

Development of the TDP43-proteinopathia cell model to search approaches to pathogenic therapy of the Frontotemporal Lobar Degeneration*

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Change in compartmentalization of TDP43 protein, loss of its nuclear localization, and the protein loading in the cytoplasm, where it forms aggregates, are the important pathogenic factors of molecular dysfunction development during the TDP43-proteinopathies. Inhibition of the pathogenic proteins aggregation is considered now as a perspective approach to development of the methods of pathogenic therapy of neurodegenerative diseases caused by the proteinopathies. Development of convenient cell models, which more adequately reproduce molecular mechanism of the proteins aggregation typical for the proteinopathies allows significant optimization of the development of compounds, which can specifically suppress or block different stages of the proteinopathy. The present work demonstrates the development of the original model of the TDP43-proteinopathy in the culture of human neuroblastoma SH-SY5Y cells with formation of typical TDP43-reactive structures, imitating histopathological inclusions, which are revealed in tissue autopsy of patients with different forms of FLD. Russian preparation Dimebon with the neuroprotective effect can inhibit formation of the TDP43-reactive inclusions in this cell model. It can be assumed as the potential compound, on the basis of which the development of methods of the pathogenic therapy of TDP43-proteinopathy is possible, and some of the FLD forms, particularly.

Key words: neurodegeneration, dementia, frontotemporal lobar degeneration, TDP43

Introduction

Frontotemporal Lobar Degeneration (FLD) belongs to the group of conformational disorders of nervous system characterized by development of proteinopathy. It is the third most common type of dementia standing after Alzheimer's and Parkinson's diseases. Recent studies showed that a DNA/RNA-binding protein TDP43 (Transactivation-responsive DNA-binding Protein-43) of 43kDa plays important role in the pathogenesis of FLD [31]. It forms active complexes necessary for pre-mRNA splicing and RNA transport to cytoplasm [31], mRNA stabilization [27] and translation [7] after binding to a number of nuclear proteins. TDP43 binding to other proteins is generally mediated through amino acid motifs in its N-terminal region. Impairment of TDP43 metabolism and function leads to development of TDP43-proteinopathy. TDP43-reactive ubiquitinated histopathological inclusions are frequently found in autopsy samples of affected nervous tissue from FLD patients [5, 19, 22]. Molecular genetic analysis of a large cohort of FLD patients revealed TDP43 mutations associated with familial FLD forms having autosomal dominant inheritance. Moreover, substantial part of idiopathic FLD forms is built up of cases of defective TLD metabolism and mutations in *tdp43* gene [23, 26]. As a component of ubiquitinated inclusions, TDP43 is found in hyperphosphorylated form [5, 10, 14, 22]. Detailed biochemical analysis of TDP43-reactive inclusions showed that histopathological inclusions mostly contain truncated 25kDa form of TDP43, which is a

product of cleavage of considerable N-terminal portion of the molecule including nuclear localization signal [35]. An established opinion currently exists, that it is this 25kDa TDP43 species resulting from caspase-dependent progranulin-mediated cleavage, that represents the main pathogenic form initiating and supporting proteinopathy.

Noteworthy, TDP43 compartmentalization change is observed also in non-proteinopathic neurodegeneration processes. For example, after axon removal in experimental mice, TDP43 redistributes inside of cells and its substantial part is detected in cytoplasm, similarly to proteinopathies, but without deposit formation [20, 21]. Substantial evidence is currently available indicating that TDP43 in neurons is involved in response to various types of stress and in post-stress repair events. For instance, histopathological changes of metabolism and compartmentalization of TDP43 without formation of histopathological inclusions were discovered in brains of patients upon hypoxia-induced oxidative stress followed by ischemic stroke [17]. Detailed biochemical study showed that during ischemic brain damage a key role in a chain of pathogenetic events leading to neurodegeneration belongs to truncated 25 kDa form of TDP43 [16]. It allowed to consider the pathogenic 25 kDa TDP43 form a potential molecular target for development of pathogenetic therapy not only for classic TDP43 proteinopathies, but for other NDD, which molecular pathogenesis includes aberrations of TDP43 metabolism, including ischemic stroke.

* Full-length human TDP43 cDNA was obtained from laboratory of M.Hasegawa (Tokio, Japan).

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Materials and methods

Dimebon. 3,6-dimethyl-9-(2-methyl-pyridyl-5)-ethyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-gamma-carboline dihydrochloride was manufactured by joint stock company «Organika», Novokuznetsk [36–38].

Cell culture. Adhesive continuous cell line of human neuroblastoma SH-SY5Y was obtained from European Collection of Cell Cultures (ECACC). Cells were plated on collagen coated coverslips (Collagen Type IV, Sigma, USA) of 10 mm diameter. SH-SY5Y neuronal differentiation was stimulated by retinoic acid (all-trans retinoic acid, Sigma, USA) in the final concentration of 10 μM. Cells were used before they undergo twenty passages.

Expression vector was generated by insertion of 5'-truncated coding cDNA sequence of human TDP43 [Δ3-192] to the *pEGFP-C1* expression vector using XhoI-EcoRI restriction sites. Transient transfection of cell cultures was performed with Lipofectamine 2000 (Invitrogen, USA).

Immunofluorescence. Cells were fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde and then treated with methanol. After washing with PBS and blocking in 5% goat serum/PBS/Triton X100 for one hour, cells were incubated with primary antibodies (1:1000 dilution) against beta-actin (mouse polyclonal, Sigma, USA) diluted in blocking solution and then with secondary anti-mouse immunoglobulin antibody (Alexa, Molecular probes, Invitrogen, USA) in 1:1000 dilution. Nuclei were counterstained with DAPI. Data collection and analysis were done using Leica DMI 4000 B fluorescent microscope. Microphotographs were obtained with Leica DFS 490 camera and Leica Application Suite 2.8.1 software (Leica Microsystems, Germany).

Counting of SH-SY5Y cells containing TDP43 inclusions.

Transient transfection of cell cultures was performed with either TDP43-coding plasmid [Δ3-192] or empty pEGFP-C1 vector under equivalent conditions. 5 serial dilutions of TDP43 vector with 25% decrement of DNA concentration were used. The number of green fluorescent cells was counted in three random square regions [100×100 μm] of a culture dish 4 hours after transfection with TDP43-coding vector [Δ3-192]. In the same way the number of green fluorescent cells was counted for each vector dilution and the dish with identical transfection efficiency was chosen for analysis. The number of cells with inclusions was then counted in the chosen dish 4, 12, 24 and 48 hours after transfection.

Aggregates count. Cultured cells were fixed 16 hours after Dimebon addition and the number of fluorescent inclusions of 5 μm diameter and larger was counted. All coverslip area was scanned and the mean of three individual coverslips was calculated. A pair of values was obtained in each experiment: in Dimebon-treated cells (experimental value) and in non-treated cells (control value). Statistical analysis was performed using Student's t-test for dependent samples. Inclusions number in Dimebon-treated cell cultures was represented as a percentage of control values.

Fractionation of detergent-insoluble fractions was performed as previously described [2].

Results

Cytoplasmic TDP43 inclusions formation in SH-SY5Y cells.

Human neuroblastoma SH-SY5Y cells were transfected with the DNA plasmid coding an aberrant TDP43 form. The *pEGFP-C1-TDP43* [Δ3-192] construct gave high synthesis rate

Fig. 1. Formation of cytoplasmic inclusions in SH-SY5Y culture by truncated TDP43 form [Δ3-192]:

A – fluorescently labeled (green) inclusions of TDP43 [Δ3-192]; B – DAPI nuclear staining (blue); C – immunohistochemical staining with anti-actin antibodies (red); D – cross-merging of images A–C; E – domain structure of pathogenic TDP43 form [Δ3-192]; GFP – green fluorescent protein; RRM – RNA binding site; NES – nuclear export signal; GR – glycine-rich region.

Number of viable cells, containing fluorescent protein, for 10 000 μm^2 area

Plasmid	Time point			
	4 h	12 h	24 h	48 h
[$\Delta 3$ -192] form	79.8 \pm 9.5	51.0 \pm 5.8	23.1 \pm 6.6	9.8 \pm 2.1
pEGFP-C1 vector	70.4 \pm 8.7	89.0 \pm 10.8	79.0 \pm 12.8	51.8 \pm 5.7

of GFP-labeled truncated TDP43 protein with inactivated functionally important domains. Mutant protein molecule lacked nuclear localization signal, first RNA binding domain, linker, and had its second RNA binding domain truncated, so that such protein accumulated in cytoplasm and aggregated (fig. 1, E). By fluorescent microscopy, exogenous protein was detected as a part of numerous disperse cytoplasmic inclusions that were transported to perinuclear space where they merged forming large inclusions (fig. 1).

These large inclusions are easy to count and analyze which makes this model favorable to test anti-aggregation properties of compounds under development. Cytoplasmic deposits formed by the truncated TDP43 protein [$\Delta 3$ -192] are morphologically close to histopathological TDP43-reactive inclusions described in Patients with a number of FLD and ALS forms.

Cytotoxicity of the aberrant TDP43 form [$\Delta 3$ -192]. Enumeration of SH-SY5Y cells containing [$\Delta 3$ -192] TDP43 inclusions performed at several time points after transfection showed that the structures forming in cytoplasm were highly toxic. Loss of cells expressing fluorescent-labeled TDP43 form [$\Delta 3$ -192] was observed as quickly as 12 hours after transfection. SH-SY5Y cells were transfected with either TDP43-coding plasmid [$\Delta 3$ -192] or control empty pEGFP-C1 vector under the same conditions. In 4 hours, first estimations were made and samples with identical transfection efficiency were chosen for further analysis 12, 24 and 48 hours after the transfection (the Table).

The number of cells received fluorescent marker protein with the vector was virtually constant over 48 hours. At the same time, loss of cells expressing pathogenic TDP43 form was observed 12 hours after transfection (57% of control). The cell number reduced 10 times compared to initial value 48 hours after transfection (19% of control). This data shows that TDP43 [$\Delta 3$ -192] having high aggregation potential and exclusively cytoplasmic localization is highly toxic for eukaryotic cells.

Inhibitory effect of Dimebon on progression of TDP43-proteinopathy in cell culture. Addition of Dimebon to growth medium of neuroblastoma culture expressing TDP43 [$\Delta 3$ -192] resulted in significant decrease in the number of cytoplasmic inclusions (fig. 2). Dimebon was added to growth medium after transfection in the final concentration of 10 μM ; fresh medium without any preparations was added to control cultures. To assess Dimebon action on differentiating neuroblasts they were treated with retinoic acid.

Figure 2 demonstrates combined results of five experiments showing that addition of Dimebon to cultured cells expressing pathogenic form of TDP43 protein significantly inhibited formation of cytoplasmic inclusions in the mixed pool of transfected cells by 55% in undifferentiated and by 53% in differentiated SH-SY5Y cultures. This data directly shows that Dimebon can inhibit development of proteinopathy caused by aggregation of pathogenic TDP43 protein form.

Study of detergent-insoluble protein fractions in SH-SY5Y cell culture after transfection with mutant TDP43 form [$\Delta 3$ -192]. Sequential fractionation of proteins in a series of buffers with different detergent concentrations was used to isolate protein fraction containing TDP43 aggregates insoluble in Triton X-100 and RIPA, which can only be dissolved by boiling in 1% SDS. TDP43 detection after fractionation was performed by immunoblotting. Figure 3 presents the results of SH-SY5Y protein fractionation after transfection with the created vector.

Discussion

We modeled TDP43 proteinopathy in human neuroblastoma cell culture forming typical cytoplasmic aggregates by means of ectopic expression of human TDP43 pathogenic form. To create the genetic construct coding this pathogenic TDP43 form, nuclear localization signal was deleted from TDP43 cDNA, because a distinctive trait of TDP43-reactive inclusions in patients is their predominantly cytoplasmic localization, whereas normally TDP43 is mainly a

Fig. 2. Dimebon influences the amount of TDP43 [$\Delta 3$ -192] inclusions in the cytoplasm of SH-SY5Y neuroblastoma cell culture. The number of inclusions in cell cultures non-differentiated (ND) and differentiated to neuronal type (D) after Dimebon addition is shown as a percentage of control. * — $p < 0.05$; Student's t-test for dependent samples, $n=5$.

Fig. 3. Analysis of TDP43 [$\Delta 3$ -192] content in detergent-insoluble fractions of total protein preparations of SH-SY5Y cells (immunoblotting): HS — soluble protein fraction; T/R — fraction of proteins soluble in presence of Triton X-100 or RIPA buffer @; S — detergent-insoluble protein structure.

nuclear protein. Consequently, the pathogenic TDP43 form lost its nuclear localization which determined its deposition in cytoplasm. Moreover, the created pathogenic form lacked the first RNA-binding domain and the structure of the second RNA-binding domain was disrupted. This makes it impossible for the aberrant forms to perform one of the main functions of RNA metabolism regulation. Ectopically expressed truncated pathogenic TDP43 form [Δ3-192] with impaired function and compartmentalization accumulates in cytoplasm of cultured cells, aggregates and forms deposits, thus reproducing molecular-cellular pathology seen during histopathological analysis of samples from patients with a number of FLD and ALS forms characterized by the presence of TDP43-reactive histopathological inclusions, in human neuroblastoma cell culture. Importantly, the leading role in the inclusion formation belongs to truncated aberrant 25 kDa forms of TDP43 which are detected by various methods in biological samples from patients together with normal 43 kDa form. And it is this truncated protein that is present in aggregated state [15]. That is why the model system created by us is optimized for searching and testing of compounds capable of inhibiting the formation of TDP43-reactive inclusions containing truncated pathogenic protein species. Exactly this kind of models is needed to develop methods of pathogenetic therapy of TDP43 proteinopathies. TDP43 aggregates [Δ3-192] form rapidly, they are large, and such inclusions are easy to analyze. This pathogenic form of the protein appeared to be highly toxic, and cells transfected with the vector containing TDP43 [Δ3-192] sequence die in 12 hours after transfection, whereas in control cultures transfected with the empty vector cell mortality was not detected (the Table).

It was previously shown that in course of aggregation of mutant forms of potentially amyloidogenic TDP43 protein, detergent-insoluble fibrillary structures are forming that can be detected in affected tissues of patients as well as *in vitro* [11, 29]. Moreover, these structures are reproduced in different experimental systems: transgenic animals [30] and cell cultures [33]. Electron microscopy shows that these structures do not match amyloid type characteristics [3–4]. Furthermore, histopathological inclusions composed of these fibrillary structures are not stained with classical amyloid dyes Congo Red and Thioflavin S. Therefore histopathological inclusions of non-amyloid type have been described by the present moment in all studied models of TDP43 proteinopathy as well as autopsy material from patients with TDP43-proteinopathies.

High amount of soluble TDP43 forms is detected in cytoplasmic fraction in our model, which speaks for active synthesis of exogenous protein. Substantial part of it shortly aggregates into «heavy» fibrils that precipitate during centrifugation at 80 000g but do not represent the terminal aggregation product as long as they are soluble in the presence of Triton X-100. It is important that [Δ3-192] TDP43 form can produce detergent-insoluble aggregates, because deposition of insoluble forms is an important indicator of proteinopathy progression.

One of approaches in development of proteinopathy pathogenetic therapy is establishment of balance between detergent-insoluble forms of aggregating proteins in cells, therefore our cellular model of TDP43-proteinopathy can be used to evaluate this parameter during drug testing.

One of the most important practical issues is development of validation method for inhibitory action of neuroprotective compounds on TDP43-proteinopathy progression. It was pre-

viously shown that Dimebon restricted proteinopathy progression caused by various potentially amyloidogenic proteins. Dimebon inhibited progression of gamma-synucleinopathy in transgenic mice model by slowing formation of gamma-synuclein-reactive histopathological inclusions in affected nervous tissue regions of model animals [1, 6]. Dimebon also effectively inhibited alpha-synucleinopathy progression in both cell and transgenic animal models by slowing formation speed of insoluble α -synuclein-reactive cytoplasmic inclusions, including Lewi bodies [43]. Similar data was obtained in study of Dimebon action on model proteinopathies caused by aggregation of A β -peptides and tau protein [39, 41].

The fact that Dimebon is able to inhibit proteinopathy caused by absolutely different in properties aggregation-prone proteins allows to suggest that its action is likely to be directed on general protective mechanisms and is independent from the particular type of potentially amyloidogenic protein. Study of Dimebon influence on TDP43 aggregation demonstrated that it can inhibit formation of cytoplasmic TDP43 aggregates [33]. Histological analysis showed that therapeutic action of Dimebon is based on the influence on the amount of insoluble aggregated forms of pathogenic peptides [2, 33]. Nevertheless molecular mechanisms and exact targets of Dimebon action were not revealed. Moreover, aberrant proteins used to mimic TDP43-proteinopathy formed cytoplasmic inclusions that were morphologically distinct from those detected in FLD and ALS patients during histopathological examination.

An important applied scientific task is a study of drug action on mature neuron cell cultures which are considered to be more appropriate model systems than undifferentiated cells, even possessing many important neuron properties. Therefore we investigated inhibitory effect of Dimebon on proteinopathy in both undifferentiated cell cultures and cultures stimulated to differentiate to neuronal cell type. The results demonstrated that Dimebon is able to inhibit aggregation of the mutant TDP43 form in differentiated cells with the same effectiveness as in undifferentiated cells (fig. 2).

Considerable body of evidence has been recently obtained by a number of laboratories confirming neuroprotective activity of Dimebon and several other compounds of carboline group. At the same time, the question of particular molecular mechanisms of action of these compounds is still open. Aside from inhibition of H1 and H2 receptors [40], Dimebon also suppresses butyrylcholinesterase and acetylcholinesterase activity [32], blocks potential-dependent calcium channels, N-methyl-D-aspartate receptors, adrenergic and serotonergic receptors [12], regulates mitochondrial pore opening, and also able to stabilize glutamate-induced calcium currents [12, 18] and facilitate neurogenesis in hippocampus [24]. However, none of these studies uncovered molecular targets of Dimebon that could help to explain molecular mechanism of its neuroprotective action and find out which routes does blocking of proteinopathy go resulting in slower neurodegeneration.

As we have previously shown, chronic Dimebon administration to transgenic animals with developing proteinopathy results in decreased content of detergent-insoluble forms of potentially amyloidogenic proteins in cells and ubiquitinated high molecular weight proteins in detergent-insoluble fractions [2]. At the same time, it is still not established if Dimebon acts directly on the process of protein aggregation or its effect results from activation of controlled degradation of preexisting

fibrillary protein structures, in particular, autophagosomal system. Conversely, Dimebon was shown to influence cell metabolism by promoting glucose consumption by the brain of aged mice [9] and advance cell culture survival rate during terminal differentiation to neurons through increase in mitochondrial activity [34]. Together these data suggest that Dimebon can modulate cellular response to external stress and activate components of neuronal systems of controlled degradation of aberrant protein species.

The evidence has been recently obtained proving that Dimebon can activate components of intracellular systems of controlled protein degradation, including autophagosomal system [39, 43]. Autophagy is regulated by various signaling pathways: through mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAP) cascade, PU3K-Akt-mTOR, etc. [42]. In some cases the reason of proteinopathy development followed by neurodegeneration is the loss of cell ability to remove proteins that have changed their conformation and gained pathogenic properties, as well as insoluble protein inclusions formed by them, from functional space [13].

We have previously studied Dimebon action on transcription level of *ATG5* gene coding for Atg5 protein, which initially covalently binds to Atg16 and thus forms ubiquitin-like conjugated structure having strong tropism to autophagosome membrane. Coordinated changes of expression level of all three complex components can serve as a reliable indicator of autophagy program activation. For this reason we analyzed Dimebon action on the other two elements of the complex — ATG12 and ATG16 as well [44]. Results of this study point that Dimebon modulates expression of all three genes in SH-SY5Y culture and that detected simultaneous lift in transcription levels of ATG5, ATG12 and ATG16 can evidence for autophagy stimulation.

An important element of Dimebon neuroprotective action mechanism is its influence on the functional state of mitochondria [34]. We studied *IRGM* gene expression [44]. The corresponding protein has GTPase activity, activates mitochondria division, and participates in autophagy activation [25]. We showed that Dimebon stimulates IRGM expression which correlates well with the peak of p38 kinase phosphorylation.

p38 and ERK1/2 kinases can be activated simultaneously, and p38 is able to inhibit autophagy triggered by ERK1/2 activation [8]. In the studied cell system Dimebon caused rapid rise of phosphorylated ERK1/2 and p38 amount and had not only short-term stimulatory effect, but could also exert long-lasting effects. These data show that Dimebon can stimulate autophagy in cell cultures, which is consistent with other studies [28, 39, 43].

In summary, sufficient data has been collected allowing to view Dimebon as a promising compound to develop medicines on its base for pathophysiological therapy of neurodegenerative diseases having proteinopathy as their pathogenetic basement, because it effects the key element of proteinopathy pathogenesis — accumulation of insoluble protein aggregates within pathogenetic inclusions.

Conclusions

The present work provides data on development of cellular model system reproducing key elements of molecular pathogenesis of TDP43-proteinopathy and its use for selection of neuroprotective drugs necessary to create methods of pathogenetic therapy of NDD which have TDP43 aggregations

as the main molecular-pathological component. A genetic construct was created coding for the human pathogenic TDP43 form [Δ 3-192] that gives the most relevant model of development of TDP43-reactive structures imitating histopathological inclusions detected in autopsy samples of patients with some FLD and ALS forms in human neuroblastoma SH-SY5Y cell culture.

In the created model system inhibitory effect of Dimebon on formation of TDP43-reactive inclusions was studied, and we showed that Dimebon is equally effective in reducing the number of TDP43-reactive inclusions in both non-differentiated and differentiated towards neuronal cell type SH-SY5Y cultures. Creation of appropriate model systems for studying of molecular mechanisms of FLD development and reproducing the most important aspects of FLD pathogenesis is a necessary prerequisite for progress in the field and optimization of directed search of compounds for pathophysiological FLD therapy.

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